

FIRST REPORT ON *AZOTOBACTER CHROOCOCCUM* XH2018 AND ITS EXOCELLULAR BIOPOLYMERS FOR STRESS MITIGATION IN ORGANIC COTTON PRODUCTION ON SALINE SOILS OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526832>

One of the main abiotic pressures endangering global sustainable crop production is salinity stress. By 2050, it is anticipated that approximately half of all agricultural lands worldwide will be damaged by salinity (Kumar et al., 2020). The physiological, biochemical, and molecular characteristics of plants are adversely affected by salinity stress in a variety of ways, which decreases not only soil fertility but also crop productivity. The genetic diversity, physiology, and selection of cotton (*Gossypium* spp.) in Uzbekistan have been well documented (Kushanov et al., 2022). However, there have been no prior scientific reports on organic cotton production in the region. This study marks the first attempt to evaluate the feasibility of organic cotton cultivation in Uzbekistan using microbial biofertilizers and EPS-based bio-organic treatments under salt-affected soil conditions.

The application of molasse-based *A. chroococcum* XH2018 suspension through foliar top-dressing and soil treatment significantly enhanced the physiological, morphological, and biochemical traits of cotton under saline conditions. As a plant growth-promoting bacterium, *A. chroococcum* has previously been reported to boost yield, suppress pathogens, and reduce dependence on chemical fertilizers (Gu et al., 2019; Li et al., 2023). In this study, treatment with XH2018 biomass, exopolysaccharide (EPS), and molasses significantly stimulated chlorophyll and carotenoid synthesis. Specifically, chlorophyll a and b concentrations increased by 27.86% and 59.42%, respectively, while carotenoid levels rose by 28.13%, confirming its role as a biofertilizer in stress-affected soils. The bio-organic amendment also improved agronomic parameters: cotton weight per boll increased by 12.65%, fiber weight by 10.83%, and seed number and weight by 9.4% and 13.63%, respectively. Although fiber length improved only slightly (0.38%), the overall phenotypic enhancement was significant. These morphological changes reflect adaptive, non-genotypic responses conducive to yield stability in marginal environments.

In addition to growth and yield improvements, the bio-organic treatment positively influenced oil yield and composition. Cottonseed oil per plant increased by 28.42% (from 29.36 g to 37.71 g), along with a notable rise in essential fatty acids. Linoleic acid (C18:2), the dominant unsaturated fatty acid essential for human health, increased by 30.4%, while linolenic acid (C18:3) rose by 45.04% compared to NPK treatments. These biochemical improvements highlight the nutritional benefits of cotton grown under bio-organic conditions. Moreover, the strong correlation between enhanced seed biomass and increased fatty acid yield suggests a direct relationship between agronomic performance and oil quality. Importantly, these enhancements were phenotypic, with genotypic characteristics remaining unchanged, indicating

that EPS-based biofertilization offers a sustainable strategy to improve both crop productivity and nutritional value in salt-affected agricultural systems.

REFERENCES

Gu M, Yang R, Xu W, Tang G, Zhang Z, Zhang Y, Feng L, Wang N, Zhan F. 2019. Effects of cotton stalk biochar combined with bio-organic fertilizer on rhizosphere soil microecology and cotton growth of continuous cropping cotton. *J Agric Sci Technol (Beijing)* 21(10):47–57.

Kumar A, Singh S, Gaurav AK, Srivastava S, Verma JP. 2020. Plant growth-promoting bacteria: biological tools for the mitigation of salinity stress in plants. *Front Microbiol* 11:1216. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.01216>.

Kushanov FN, Komilov DJ, Turaev OS, Ernazarova DK, Amanboyeva RS, Gapparov BM, Yu JZ. 2022. Genetic analysis of mutagenesis that induces the photoperiod insensitivity of wild cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* subsp. *purpurascens*. *Plants* 11:3012. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11223012>.

Li Z, Zhao M, Li L, Yuan YY, Chen FJ, Parajulee MN, Ge F. 2023. *Azotobacter* inoculation can enhance the resistance of Bt cotton to cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera*. *Insect Sci*.